

Perceptions and practices of the Konso community (South-west Ethiopia) relating to malaria: implications for control

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Abstract

Background. To get a deeper insight on how the Konso community in Ethiopia perceives malaria and manages the disease we assessed people's knowledge on the causes of malaria, their treatment-seeking behaviour and use of preventive measures.

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted during the period of high malaria transmission in 2009 and comprised a structured questionnaire administered to 609 family heads, focus group discussions and in-depth interviews with caretakers and traditional medical practitioners respectively.

Results. From focus group discussions (FGD) emerged that malaria is perceived as a major health problem by the Konso community. The questionnaire outcome revealed that the majority (75%) of the interviewed household heads know that malaria is transmitted by mosquitoes, but most of them (85%) associate the disease also with particular environmental and climatic conditions. Half of the respondents resort to home treatment with herbal remedies as first source of cure, most commonly by using plant parts from *Moringa stenopetala*, *Vernonia amygdalina* and *Withania somnifera*. The use of mosquito nets, cleaning the house and burning herbs emerged as the most frequently cited perceived and practiced preventive measures.

Conclusions. Since traditional methods to cure and prevent malaria are deeply rooted in the Konso community, there is an urgent need to validate efficacy and safety of the plant preparations that are employed. Community information campaigns need to pay attention to the still widely diffused misconceptions about the transmission of malaria that possibly may interfere with the proper use of insecticide treated mosquito nets.

1 Introduction

Malaria is the most important parasitic disease of man in terms of mortality, morbidity and long-term effects upon quality of life [1]. Poor and vulnerable populations are disproportionately affected by malaria and the severe consequences of the disease are borne more by the poorest [2]. Malaria is not only a major inhibitory factor of socio-economic development, by reducing the number of working days of adults but also by hindering children in their schooling and social development through absence from school and through neurological damage associated with severe episodes of the disease [3].

In Ethiopia, malaria remains a major public health problem although a substantial amount of resources is invested in the control and prevention of this parasitic disease. The main focus of current malaria control strategies in Ethiopia includes early case detection and prompt treatment of patients with artemisinin-based combination therapy (ACT), intermittent antimalarial preventive treatment during preg-

nancy, and vector control by scaling-up of long lasting insecticidal nets (LLINs) and indoor residual spraying (IRS) in targeted areas. In addition, epidemics prevention is assured by improved, early detection and warning systems [3,4].

Malaria is seasonal in most parts of Ethiopia, with unstable transmission characteristics that periodically lead to the outbreak of epidemics. More than five million clinical cases are reported yearly from governmental health facilities, indicating the enormity of the malaria menace [4]. All age groups are afflicted; the unstable character of transmission interferes with the development of clinical immunity with age. Transmission patterns vary considerably within the country, in relation to geographical (altitude) and climatic (temperature, rainfall) characteristics, and migrating populations seeking fertile land. The majority of the Ethiopian population (68%) lives in malarious lowland areas situated below 2,000 meter above sea level. There are two main malaria transmission seasons, the first lasting from March to May (short rains) and the second from September to De-

cember (long rains). The majority of cases, including epidemics, usually occur during the long rains. *Plasmodium falciparum* and *P. vivax* are the dominant parasite species and account for 60% and 40% of cases, respectively [3,5].

Disease perceptions are important determinants of health related behaviours such as treatment seeking and adherence and practice of disease prevention measures [6]. In Ethiopia, malaria perceptions are very heterogeneous, varying according to the geographical area, ethnic group, religious beliefs and cultural backgrounds. The literacy level and general modern health knowledge remains quite low in rural areas. Local traditional perceptions on malaria and the consequent health seeking and prevention related behaviours are important factors impacting the efficiency of the National Malaria Control Programme (NMCP)[7].

There is the need to reorient the national malaria control strategies presently based on a centralised "one size fits all" approach towards flexible concepts that take into consideration the particularities of the local situation [8]. A better knowledge of traditional malaria treatment, prevention practices and eventual integration of them, if proven effective, might lead to an increase in compliance by the NMCP and hence in the sustainability and cost-effectiveness of its actions.

In rural areas, the majority of the population resorts to botanical remedies to cure malaria fever and burns plants to prevent mosquito bites [9]. Given the pressing problems of non-affordability and inaccessibility to effective antimalarial drugs, traditional medicine cannot be ignored as an alternative source of treatment if proven effective [10]. The same applies to malaria prevention. Still, in many rural areas, the population relies on burning plants as the only defense against mosquito bites in the absence of LLINs.

The objective of this study was to gain a deeper understanding of the traditional malaria related knowledge and practices of the Konso ethnic group living in South-West Ethiopia. In particular it aimed to assess the community perception of malaria as a disease, traditional healing and prevention practices based on plants and attitudes to local health services. The collected information could be useful for national health policy makers and managers of the Regional Malaria Control Programme (RMCP).

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area and population

The study was conducted in the Konso District, which is situated 600 km south of Addis Ababa. The Konso District comprises 49 *kebeles* with a total population of about 235,000. The *kebele* is the lowest administrative unit in Ethiopia, assembling usually three to four traditional com-

munities (neighbourhoods). Over 90% of the district's population consists of subsistence farmers, depending heavily on rains for their agriculture [11]. Maize, millet, cassava and beans are the main crops cultivated in the area [12]. Konso people are well known for their agricultural skill of terrace farming, a unique cultivation practice that has been recognized by UNESCO as one of the world heritages.

There is one government-owned health centre in charge of the whole population of the district. At *kebele* level, health posts are instituted with a community health worker (CHW) in charge of them. In principle, malaria cases should be overseen by the CHW and treated with ACT (artemether-lumefantrine). However, due to an inefficient drug distribution system and scanty availability of the drugs this is rarely the case, and ACT supplies rarely reach the health posts. There are two private pharmacies in the district that are usually well furnished with essential drugs. ACT can be acquired there at a cost of USD 2.5 per treatment for an adult. Health centre data indicate that all inhabitants of the district are at risk and are affected by malaria, irrespective of whether they live in lowland or highland villages, since most are situated below 2000m of altitude. *Anopheles arabiensis* is the major malaria vector, whereas *An. pharaoensis* and *An. funestus* appear to be rarely implicated in malaria transmission in the area [13].

2.2 Study design and sampling techniques

The community-based health behaviour studies were conducted during the high malaria transmission season (September-December 2009), employing both quantitative and qualitative research methodologies.

The quantitative component of the study was represented by a household survey involving 609 families. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select the households representative for the district. First, six *kebeles* were selected on the basis of the distance from the district's capital and health centre to account for a) health facility proximity as a major factor influencing health seeking behaviour and b) the assumption that the level of modern health knowledge is related to the distance from the district's capital. Then, from each of the six selected *kebeles*, one out of its three to four neighbourhoods was randomly selected and 105 households were included from each neighbourhood. A trained interviewer administered a pre-tested, structured and open ended questionnaire to the head of households/spouses to collect data on socio-demographic characteristics of the interviewees and to elicit information on knowledge, beliefs, treatment seeking and preventive practices related to malaria.

The qualitative investigations were conducted in the same neighbourhoods and comprised six focus group discussions (FGD) with caretakers and in-depth interviews

with five traditional medical practitioners (TMPs). The TMPs involved were herbalists, *i.e.* their curative activities were first of all based on the preparation and administration of infusions, decoctions or macerations of plant parts and combinations of plant parts. To recruit TMPs for in-depth interviews, the snow-ball sampling technique was employed.

FGDs and in-depth interviews with TMPs were conducted by public health nurses, native Konso who are experienced in the conduct of FGD and who received additional training for this study. The inclusion criteria for community members to participate in the FGDs were: to be a household head/spouse, between 30 and 40 years of age, and to have at least one child under the age of five. The age limit was set between 30 and 40 to ensure active participation of all discussants, as it would not be so if elderly discussants were included. In the Konso community elderly people are given priority to speak out during discussions.

FGDs were conducted in three *kebeles* namely Fuchucha, Dokato and Arfaide, with separate sessions for female and male care takers. All the six FGDs were arranged in groups of 8 to 12 and lasted 45-60 minutes.

2.3 Data analysis

Questionnaire answers were categorised and coded before data entry and all data were entered and analysed using SPSS version 15.0 for Windows. Frequencies and proportions were calculated for the descriptive data analysis. Associations between participant's characteristics and malaria-related knowledge and practices were analysed using the Chi square test, considering an association significant when a P-value of <0.05 was obtained. Qualitative data were transcribed and analysed manually and the views shared by a majority of FGD participants and statements of TMPs considered innovative were selected to be quoted to complement and illustrate the results.

2.4 Ethical approval

Ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Ethical Review Committee of South Nations, Nationalities and Peoples Regional Government Health Bureau, Ethiopia. Written informed consent was obtained from the study participants before research instruments (questionnaires, FGDs, interviews with TMPs) were administered. All information obtained from participants was treated as confidential.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents who participated in the household study.

Characteristics	Frequency (n, %)		
	Male	Female	All respondents
Total	211 (34.7)	398 (65.3)	609 (100)
Age			
15-24	25 (11.8)	80 (20.1)	105 (17.2)
25-34	66 (31.3)	137 (34.4)	203 (33.3)
35-44	45 (21.3)	92 (23.1)	137 (22.5)
45-54	32 (15.2)	62 (15.6)	94 (15.4)
>55	43 (20.4)	27 (6.8)	70 (11.5)
Marital status			
Married	204 (96.6)	364 (91.5)	568 (92.3)
Single	3 (1.4)	2 (0.5)	5 (0.8)
Divorced	1 (0.5)	4 (1.0)	5 (0.8)
Widowed	2 (0.9)	20 (5.0)	22 (3.6)
Separated	1 (0.5)	8 (2.0)	9 (1.5)
Educational status^a			
Never been to school	149 (70.6)	319 (80.2)	468 (76.8)
Can read & write	9 (4.3)	13 (3.3)	22 (3.6)
Grade 1-3	32 (15.2)	34 (8.5)	66 (10.9)
Grade 4-6	13 (6.2)	15 (3.8)	28 (4.6)
Grade 7-9	6 (2.8)	12 (3.0)	18 (2.9)
Grade 10-12	2 (0.9)	4 (1.0)	6 (1.0)
College	2 (0.9)	2 (0.5)	4 (0.7)
Occupation^b			
Farmer	195 (92.4)	255 (64.1)	450 (73.9)
Housewife	0 (0)	126 (31.6)	126 (20.7)
Student	4 (1.9)	7 (1.8)	11 (1.9)
Daily labourer	2 (0.9)	5 (1.3)	7 (1.2)
Trader	2 (0.9)	5 (1.3)	7 (1.2)
Gov/NGO ^c employee	1 (0.5)	4 (1.0)	5 (0.8)
Metal work	3 (1.4)	0 (0)	3 (0.5)

^a Grade 1-6 = primary school; Grade 7-9 = junior secondary school; Grade 9-12 = secondary school. ^b Respondents were prompted to tell only one major duty they assume. ^c Government/non-government.

3 Results

3.1 Socio-demographic characteristics of interviewees

Of the 630 households selected for the study, 609 participated, yielding a response rate of 96.7%. The mean age of the respondents was 36 (s.d. 13.5; median 34). Women were more frequently available for interviews at home than their male counterparts. Most of the participants were farmers (males: 92.4%; females: 64.1%) and were illiterate (males: 70.6%; females: 80.2%). The mean size of the respondent families was seven. Details on the socio-demographic characteristics are shown in Table 1.

A total of 66 residents from three of the six study neighbourhoods were involved in the six FGD sessions. Of these participants, 35 were female and 31 were male care takers. The 19 discussants from Dokato *kebele* were literate (8 males, 11 females), whereas the 47 discussants from Arfaide (12 males, 12 females) and Fuchucha *kebele* (11 males, 12 females) were illiterate. The median age of focus group discussants was 34. A total of five in-depth inter-

views were conducted with TMPs. All of them were elderly males, the youngest stated to be 48 years old.

3.2 Perception of malaria

The majority of the subjects interviewed in the household study (73.6%) stated that malaria is a major health problem in the area. Over the last 2 years interviewees suffered on average 6 times from what they interpreted as a clinical malaria episode (range 1-12), once or twice in each of the two transmission seasons. The relevance of the disease for the Konso population was also highlighted by caretakers during FGD through statements like: *"the most common disease that is making the life of our community wretched is malaria"* (Dokato kebele) or *"In our history there is nothing like malaria that afflicted our people without discrimination, it affects children, it affects elderly, it affects men and women"* (Arfaide kebele).

Analysis of the FGDs revealed that uncomplicated malaria usually is referred to as *bineada* and the severe form of the disease as *elekefemae*. The latter is mainly associated with the symptoms of cerebral malaria and convulsions. *Bineada* is sometimes also used as a general term for malaria, comprising all manifestations of the disease as in modern science terminology; people know the correct symptoms of mild and severe malaria and have names for these conditions.

Prompted for malaria symptoms, the majority of the respondents proved to be familiar with the most frequent symptoms such as headache, chills and fever (Figure 1). From the FGDs it emerged that most caretakers knew that severe malaria (*elekefemae*) evolves from the mild form (*bineada*), stating for example: *"Sometimes bineada can turn into elekefemae and this form is not amenable to home treatment"* (Dokato kebele). Caretakers also know that severe malaria is a life-threatening disease: *"Bineada that moves on to elekefemae is dangerous; many people died of it in our community"* (Arfaide kebele).

3.3 Perceived causes of malaria

The causes and transmission of malaria were frequently associated with staying in particular environments or being exposed to particular climatic conditions. However, a substantial proportion of the heads of households related the disease also to mosquito bites. Most frequently, respondents associated staying in lowland areas (86.9%) and staying in swampy areas (84.2%) with getting malaria (Table 2). This perception emerged also from the FGD: *"When a person is going to lowland areas for farming and is staying there, she/he will be exposed to the heat of the sun, will sweat a lot and lots of sweating causes dryness of the body and eventually malaria"* (Fuchucha kebele).

Figure 1. Malaria signs and symptoms mentioned by the interviewees (n=609) of the household study and frequency of citation of each symptom. Respondents often cited more than one symptom.

Table 2. Causes of malaria reported by the household study participants.

Causes of malaria	# of responses	Frequency (%)
Staying in lowland areas	529	86.9
Staying in swampy areas	513	84.2
Exposure to cold weather	476	78.2
Mosquito bites	459	75.4
Drinking dirty water	332	54.5
Exposure to too much sun	167	27.5
Close contact with a malaria patient	150	24.6

On the other hand, mosquito bites as a cause of malaria was cited by 75% of the interviewees (Table 2). The frequency of stating correctly mosquito bites as a cause of malaria was inversely associated with the distance from the health care facilities ($P < 0.05$). Among the literate respondents, 79.4% associated mosquitoes with malaria. This knowledge was only slightly less frequent among the illiterate interviewees, (74.1%; $P > 0.05$). Most of the respondents (82.5%) between the ages of 35 - 44 years linked mosquito bites with malaria, among the elderly population (> 55 years) a significantly smaller proportion (65.7%) had this knowledge ($P < 0.05$). Gender of the respondents did not influence this knowledge. This community appeared aware of malaria whether literate or illiterate and regardless of gender.

3.4 Treatment seeking behaviour

As a first source of treatment, about half of the study participants mentioned to resort to home treatment with herbal remedies, while the other half stated to address themselves to the government owned health care facility (GHF) (Figure 2). The choice of the first line resource was found to be associated with the distance from the district's capital ($P < 0.05$). Fifty one percent of the households of Arfaide *kebele*, which is situated in close proximity (5km) to the district's capital, sought treatment at the GHF. This proportion dropped to 40% of the respondents from the most remote Fuchucha *kebele* (22km from the district's capital).

A small proportion cited to resort to pharmacies (all located in the district capital), or to TMPs. For the ones who chose to treat themselves with herbal remedies at home, the reported absence of medicines from the GHF was the most commonly accounted reason for this decision (36.9%). This attitude also frequently emerged from FGDs: "Going to the health care facilities to get a solution for malaria is almost a waste of time; those facilities are always running out of medicines. Therefore we prefer to treat it in our place (=at home) with herbal remedy (Dokato *kebele*). "When we recognise that someone has got malaria, we prepare a special kind of chowder from leaves of Haleko (Moringa), butter and bones of sheep or goat and the sick person drinks it." (Fuchucha *kebele*).

About half of the respondents (55.5%) reported that they start treatment within 24 hours of suspecting a malaria episode, one third of respondents indicated to do so within two to three days, while the remainders stated to initiate cure only after the fourth day of disease onset.

Indications on the second line treatment seeking choices differed considerably between the households that chose home treatment with herbal remedies as a first resource and the ones that preferred to seek help directly at the GHF (Figure 2). Half of the respondents (50.9%) belonging to the

Figure 2. First line and second line source of treatment reported by interviewees of the household study, Konso District, Ethiopia. Pie (circle) stands for the 1st line sources of treatment. Left column represents 2nd line sources of treatment mentioned by those (46%) who resort to GHF as 1st line source. Right column stands for the 2nd line sources of treatment mentioned by those (48%) who resort to home treatment with herbal remedies as 1st line source. GHF= Government owned health care facility, TMP = Traditional medical practitioners.

Table 3. Plants used to treat malaria as stated by traditional medical practitioners.

Vernacular name	Scientific name	Family	Parts used
Haleko (Shelaqta)	<i>Moringa stenopetala</i>	Moringaceae	Leaves & roots
Pitercama	<i>Turraea mombassana</i>	Meliaceae	Roots
Fashayta	<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i>	Asteraceae	Leaves, roots & bark
Chemotita (Gizawa)	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	Solanaceae	Leaves & roots
Maqayta	<i>Euclea divinorum</i>	Ebenaceae	Roots
Kuneyta	<i>Hypoestes forskalei</i>	Acanthaceae	Leaves & roots
Feto	<i>Lepidium sativum</i>	Brassicaceae	Seeds
Hadawa	<i>Ficus platyphylla</i>	Moraceae	Bark
Malgissa	<i>Crabbea velutina</i>	Acanthaceae	Leaves
Zigba	<i>Afrocarpus gracillior</i>	Podocarpaceae	Leaves

first group continue to resort to traditional medicine seeking help from TMP, but a considerable proportion (43%) stated to go to GHF if home treatment with herbal remedies is unsuccessful. This attitude emerged also during FGD "Some kind of malaria like the *elekefemae* is usually not resolved with home treatment; if the malaria is advancing to *elekefemae*, we take the patient to the health center" (Arfaide kebele). A large proportion (70.7%) of those who chose in the first place to address themselves to the GHF expressed the disposition to stick to this choice also for second line treatment (Figure 2).

3.5 Species of plants used to cure malaria

A considerable number of plant species were cited by TMPs, as being able to cure malaria (Table 3). TMPs reported to employ in the remedies different parts of the plants and that sometimes they are also combining two or more plant species. "Seeds of *Lepidium sativum* and dried bark of *Ficus platyphylla* decoction is effective against *bineada* and other diseases..." (TMP, Arfaide kebele). All of the interviewed TMPs mentioned *Moringa stenopetala*, *Vernonia amygdalina* and *Withania somnifera* as frequently used plants to heal malaria. Furthermore, TMPs testified that *Moringa stenopetala* is a very popular antimalarial plant and preparations of it are commonly used by caretakers for home treatment.

3.6 Preventive measures

Malaria was perceived as a preventable disease by 83.1% of the household respondents. Among the preventive methods mentioned the use of mosquito nets was most frequently cited (Table 4). Most of the respondents (80.6%) stated that utilising a mosquito net is essential to prevent malaria and a large part of the respondents (60.3%) declared to currently use a net. However, direct observation during data collection suggested that nets frequently were not properly used. Instead of finding them fixed to the ceiling over the bed, as is the case when nets are in use, it was common to see nets

Table 4. House hold study respondents' knowledge on malaria prevention and practice of cited preventive measures.

Preventive measures	Reported knowledge		Reported practice	
	# of responses	%	# of responses	%
Using mosquito nets	491	80.6	357	60.3
Cleaning the houses	214	35.1	0	0
Generating smoke in the house	124	20.4	159	26.1
Draining of water from living area	123	20.1	97	15.1
Spraying DDT	115	18.9	0	0
Staying night indoors	33	5.6	0	0
Avoiding to go to lowland areas	25	4.1	0	0
Eating good food	15	2.5	0	0
Screening openings	15	2.5	0	0
Use of repellents on skin	13	2.1	58	9.5
Closing doors & windows	0	0	23	3.8
Spraying Aerosol	9	1.5	38	6.2

0 = No one reported the knowledge or practical use of that preventive measure.

employed as bed sheets (18% of interviewees who declared to currently use a mosquito net) or to find them applied for sieving *Eragrostis tef*, a staple crop in Ethiopia (20% of the household who reported to currently use a mosquito net).

Additionally, in many households nets were found to be torn (15% of the households who declared to currently use a mosquito net) as a consequence of installing them on coarse bed constructions or because of using them for years. The proper utilisation of mosquito nets in the area is hampered by the fact that most Konso people are sleeping either on mattresses made of straw or directly on the floor. When prompted on the issue, respondents frequently forwarded the problem of cost, disabling them to equip family members with proper beds and acquire mosquito nets for all of them. The problem of affordability of mosquito nets was also emphasized during FGDs by caretakers: "Rich people who can afford to buy new mosquito nets are able to prevent malaria, but most of us are unfortunate and we cannot buy mosquito nets and thus we are suffering from malaria" (Fuchucha kebele). Ethiopia distributes LLINs for free but in the Konso District net distribution was launched only once five years ago and there was no other distribution round up to the time of data collection for the current study.

Generating smoke inside houses to drive away mosquitoes was practiced by 26.1% of respondents and a considerable variety of materials were in use. Most of these were parts of plants or whole plants (Table 5) growing in the premises of the residential areas. *Olea europaea* was preferred as it produces a pleasant aroma when burned, in addition to its reported mosquito repellent effect.

Table 5. Plants cited for generating smoke inside houses and frequency of use by participants in the household study. NA = Not applicable.

Vernacular name	Scientific name	Percent users (# responses)
Woirra	<i>Olea europaea</i>	26.4 (42)
Bahirzaf	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	21.4 (34)
Woibetta	<i>Perilalia brownii</i>	10.7 (17)
Mekayta	<i>Euclea divinorum</i>	9.4 (15)
Kinchib	<i>Euphorbia tirucalli</i>	8.8 (14)
Birbirta	<i>Cupressus lusitanica</i>	6.3 (10)
Any wood	NA	6.9 (11)
Non-plant materials	NA	10.1 (16)

4 Discussion

The present study allowed us to obtain a deeper understanding of malaria perception by the Konso people and of their practices to cure and prevent the disease. Given the high percentage of illiteracy of this population, the frequency at which the interviewees were referring to mosquito bites as the cause of malaria was surprisingly high (75%) compared with 47.5% of promptings found in an urban area of Assosa Zone, Western Ethiopia, where the majority (80%) of the respondents were literate [14]. The good knowledge observed in our study might have been laid down by information campaigns conducted by the RMCP during the last two decades. However, believes which relate malaria to environmental and climatic conditions - like, e.g. "staying in lowland areas" where people are "exposed to sweltering sun" - are also still widely diffused in the Konso culture. The association of malaria with the lowland area environment is explainable. Rains and hence *Anopheles* mosquitoes are more abundant in these areas and as a consequence farmers migrating to these areas during the rainy season for agricultural activities are more at risk of acquiring malaria compared to the individuals remaining in the highland areas. Similarly, relating malaria to sunlight exposure can be explained by the geographical and temporal association of field works with the lowland area and rainy season. However, this assertion remains hypothetical since there are no data on mosquito densities, transmission intensity and malaria incidence available for the low- and highland areas. Such environment or climate-related misconceptions are common in many rural areas of sub-Saharan Africa, where it is observed that people associate malaria with the exposure to cold weather, dirty environment, excessive heat and wind rather than mosquitoes [14-16]. This implies that the preventive measures taken are not only directed towards preventing mosquito bites but also to envi-

ronmental and climatic conditions and consequently control campaigns implemented by the NMCP may be less successful when promoting mosquito control measures.

The residents of the rural Konso District demonstrated to possess a good level of knowledge on the common symptoms of malaria. Fever, chills and headache were mentioned by the majority of the interviewees. In a previous investigation conducted in Southern Ethiopia [17], members of a rural community were found to be similarly conscious about the typical malaria symptoms: 89.7% and 87.5% of the respondents mentioned fever and headache, respectively. Whereas mild malaria is correctly recognised in most endemic African countries, in some areas people believe that severe malaria is caused by supernatural forces. For instance, in a study conducted in Tanzania [18], with the aim to determine the role of traditional healers in the management of severe malaria in children, caretakers believed that severe malaria is caused by bad spirits and that before seeking treatment at the health care facilities, the bad spirits must be removed. In contrast, it emerged from our study that the Konso people know that severe malaria follows the mild form of the same disease and hence caretakers are more likely to seek timely assistance at an appropriate modern health facility and thus to avoid the consequences of severe malaria.

Accessing care from a variety of sources is a common practice in malaria-endemic areas. In the Konso District there appears to be no clear preference for either modern or traditional medicine. In this study about half of caretakers indicated to directly address themselves to the GHF, whereas the other half indicated to start treatment at home with herbal preparations and to seek help from GHF or TMPs only if home treatment is not effective. This pattern of treatment-seeking behaviour is widespread in Africa [16]. For instance, in a rural Sudanese area the majority of mothers were found to start treatment at home with herbal remedies and to shift to health workers only if there was no response to the home treatment [19].

The reasons underlying treatment decisions are multiple and varied. In our study area, the culturally anchored beliefs and preferences of the Konso community most likely are strongly influencing their choices. However, also real life obstacles, such as the distance to be covered to reach the GHF and the chronic shortage of antimalarial drugs there [29], encourages people to resort to alternatives like home management with herbal medications. The association observed between the first sources of treatment and the distance from the District's capital suggests that the proportion of the community resorting to GHF as a first tire would be bigger if drugs were more widely available and closer to the population.

For more than a decade, ITNs have been widely promoted and distributed in sub-Saharan countries including

Ethiopia. Therefore, the high level of knowledge on the use of this protective measure, demonstrated by the respondents in this study, was not surprising. Most likely this awareness results from specific and successful promotion activities conducted by the RMCP and NMCP over the last decade. Widespread knowledge on malaria vectors and ITN use was recently also documented in southern Ethiopia. In the Wonago district, 97.5% of interviewed mothers knew that sleeping under ITNs is beneficial [20]. From our study, however, a considerable discrepancy emerged between knowledge and practice. Nets were frequently observed to be misused as bed sheets or sieves, and in households where nets were used beds were often not present, hindering their proper use. In addition, nets were often in a very poor state, torn by the coarse straw mattresses on which people usually sleep. Due to the prohibitive cost of ITNs (USD 2-4, depending on the type and size) to the rural population with a mean monthly income of less than USD 2 per capita [27], nets were rarely replaced, which is a problem hampering ITN implementation across Africa [21]. In the Konso area there is an urgent need for scaling up free net distribution in order to adhere to the universal coverage policy in endemic African countries [28]. However, for the Konso community nets should be provided with a reinforced bottom to resist wear and tear under prevailing conditions.

Plants have been employed since ancient times and still nowadays are widely used to repel/kill blood sucking insects in African countries [22]. Also in our study area, burning of herbs inside houses and in the court is widely practiced to deter mosquitoes. This practice may constitute an important complement to ITN's, providing protection against outdoor and early evening biting *Anopheles* females, when people are staying in front of their houses or gathering at particular "chatting places" in the village. Interestingly, most of the plants cited as mosquito repellents are species known and distributed throughout the country. For instance *Woirra* (*Olea europaea*), frequently cited by our study population, is also used by the Oromo ethnic group in Ethiopia. For this plant, experimental evidence on its efficacy is available: burning *Woirra* leaves drove out about 80% of *An. arabiensis* mosquitoes (the major malaria vector in Ethiopia) from an experimental cage through a specially devised escape hole [23].

The widescale use of plants as mosquito repellents has been documented in several African countries. For example a nation-wide survey in Malawi showed that 64% of residents burn wood, leaves or dung [24], 13% of rural Zimbabweans use plants [25], and almost all Kenyans living on Rusinga Island and Rambira area in Western Kenya burn plants to drive away mosquitoes from their houses [26].

In the Konso area availability, affordability and effectiveness of burning plants were the most commonly given reasons to resort to this traditional method. As this habit

seems to be deeply rooted in the culture of the Konso people, the RMCP may consider its deliberate integration into the current vector control strategies after trustable efficacy and safety data are obtained.

In conclusion, this study allowed us to obtain insight into the knowledge and beliefs of Konso people on malaria and on the role of traditional medicine practices in the control of the disease. Konso people appeared to have good knowledge about the cause of malaria as well as on treatment and preventive measures, most likely a result of the campaigns led by RMCP and NMCP over the last decade. It is our hope that the results of this study will assist the national health policy makers and managers of the NMCP in developing communication and implementation activities, tailored to the needs of the Konso people and to the particular situation of the District. The accurate knowledge of the Konso people could be materialised by bringing the drugs closer to the community and by assuring regular distribution of LLINs. Given the widespread use of plants for the treatment of patients or as mosquito repellents, studies to estimate the effectiveness and verify the safety of these plants are urgently needed. The development of improved plant-based remedies and repellents and the integration of such traditional tools in the NMCP may contribute to increased cost-effectiveness, compliance and sustainability.

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References

1. United Nations. The Millennium Development Goals Report 2005. United Nations. <http://www.un.org/docs/summit2005/MDGBook.pdf>.
2. Barat LM, Palmer N, Basu S, Worrall E, *et al.*: Do malaria control interventions reach the poor? A view through the equity lens. *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 2004, **71**:174-178.
3. National Five Years Strategic Plan for Malaria Control in Ethiopia: 2006 - 2010, Ministry of Health, 2005. <http://www.dagethiopia.org/Public/Publications/National%20Five%20Year%20Strategic%20Plan%20for%20Malaria%20Prevention%20&%20%5B1%5D.pdf>.
4. Deressa W, Ali A, Enquessellie F: Self-treatment of malaria in rural communities, Butajira, southern Ethiopia. *Bull. World Health Organ.* 2003, **81**:261-268.

5. Ethiopian National Malaria Indicator Survey. Technical summary. Federal Republic of Ethiopia. Ministry of Health 2007. http://www.cartercenter.org/resources/pdfs/news/health_publications/malaria/Ethiopia_MIS-2007_Technical_Summary.pdf.
6. Leventhal H, Benyamini Y, Brownlee S, Diefenbach M, *et al.*: Illness representations: theoretical foundations. In: Petrie KJ, Weinman JA. (Eds.) Perceptions of health and illness. Harwood Academic, Amsterdam. 1997, pp. 155-188.
7. Agyepong, IA: Malaria: Ethnomedical perceptions and practice in an Adange farming community and implications for control. *Soc. Sci. Med.* 1992, **35**:131-137.
8. Report of a WHO Study Group on the Implementation of the Global Plan of Action for Malaria Control 1993-2000. World Health Organization, Geneva. Technical Report Series, No 839.
9. Lambert J: Ethiopia: Traditional medicine and the bridge to better health. World Bank, IK Note, 2001, 35 pp. <http://www.worldbank.org/Afr/dfefault.htm>.
10. Willcox ML, Bodeker G: Traditional herbal medicines for malaria. *BMJ* 2004, **329**: 1156-1159.
11. Summary and Statistical Report of the 2007 Population and Housing Census Results. Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia Population Census Commission. http://www.csa.gov.et/pdf/Cen2007_firstdraft.pdf.
12. Shinn DH, Ofcansky TP, Prouty C: Historical Dictionary of Ethiopia. In: Konso people and language. Scarecrow Press, 2004, 242 pp.
13. Tirados I, Costantini C, Gibson G, Torr SJ: Blood-feeding behaviour of the malaria mosquito *Anopheles arabiensis*: implications for vector control. *Med. Vet. Entomol.* 2006, **20**:425-437.
14. Legesse Y, Tegegn A, Belachew T, Tushune K: Knowledge, attitude and practice about malaria transmission and its preventive measures among households of Assosa Zone, Western Ethiopia. *Ethiop. J. Health Dev.* 2000, **21**:157-165.
15. Okeke TA, Okafor HU. Perception and treatment seeking for malaria in Rural Nigeria: Implications for control. *J. Hum. Ecol.* 2008, **24**: 215-222.
16. Maslove DM, Mnyusiwalla A, Mills EJ, McGowan J, *et al.*: Barriers to the effective treatment and prevention of malaria in Africa: A systematic review of qualitative studies. *BMC Int. Health Hum. Rights* 2009, **9**:26.
17. Deressa W, Ali A, Enquoselassie F: Knowledge, attitude and practice about malaria, the mosquito and antimalarial drug in a rural community. *Ethiop. J. Health Dev.* 2003, **17**: 99-104.
18. Makundi EA, Malebo HM, Mhame P, Kitua AY, *et al.*: Role of traditional healers in the management of severe malaria among children below five years of age: the case of Kilosa and Handeni Districts, Tanzania. *Malar. J.* 2006, **5**:58.
19. Malik MA, Hinaf K, Ali SH, Ahmed ES, *et al.*: Treatment-seeking behaviour for malaria in children under five years of age: implication for home management in rural areas with high seasonal transmission in Sudan. *Malar. J.* 2006, **5**:60.
20. Dagne G, Deressa W: Knowledge and utilization of insecticide treated mosquito nets among freely supplied households in Wonago Woreda, Southern Ethiopia. *Ethiop. J. Health Dev.* 2008, **22**: 34-41.
21. Pettifor A, Taylor E, David N, Duvall S, *et al.*: Bednet ownership, use and perceptions among women seeking antenatal care in Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC): Opportunities for improved maternal and child health. *BMC Public Health* 2008, **8**:331.
22. Karunamoorthi K, Ramanujam S, Rathinasamy R: Evaluation of leaf extracts of *Vitexnegundo L.* (Family: Verbenaceae) against larvae of *Culex tritaeniorhynchus* and repellent activity on adult vector mosquitoes. *Parasitol. Res.* 2008, **103**:545-550.
23. Karunamoorthi K, Mulelam A, Wassie F: Laboratory evaluation of traditional insect/mosquito repellent plants against *Anopheles arabiensis*, the predominant malaria vector in Ethiopia. *Parasitol. Res.* 2008, **103**:529-534.
24. Ziba C, Slutsker L, Chitsulo L, Steketee RW: Use of malaria prevention measures in Malawian households. *Trop. Med. Parasitol.* 1994, **45**:70-73.
25. Lukwa N, Nyazema NZ, Curtis CF, Mwaiko GL, *et al.*: People's perceptions about malaria transmission and control using mosquito repellent plants in a locality in Zimbabwe. *Cent. Afr. J. Med.* 1999, **45**:64-68.
26. Seyoum A, Palsson K, Kunga S, Kabiru EW, *et al.*: Traditional use of mosquito-repellent plants in western Kenya and their evaluation in semi-field experimental huts against *Anopheles gambiae*: ethnobotanical studies and application by thermal expulsion and direct burning. *Trans. R. Soc. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 2000, **96**:225-231.
27. World fact book: <https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-factbook/geos/et.html>
28. WHO: Insecticide treated mosquito nets: a position statement Global Malaria Programme, World Health Organization, 2007 Aug, Geneva: <http://www.who.int/entity/malaria/publications/atoz/itnspospaperfinal/en/index.html>
29. Roll Back Malaria. http://rbm.who.int/countryaction/ethiopia_roadmap.html.

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